

78.1; H, 10.9; N, 3.5. $C_{27}H_{45}NO_3$ requires: C, 78.0; H, 10.8; N, 3.4%; ν_{max} 1545, 1465 and 1375 cm^{-1} (non-conjugated NO_2); δ 5.88 (br, s, C4-vinyl proton), 4.56 (dd, J_{ae} 4, J_{ee} 2 Hz, C6- α H), 1.16 (C10- CH_3), 0.7 (C13- CH_3), 0.9 and 0.87 (other methyl protons).

Under similar reaction conditions (same amounts of reactants were used in each case) the nitroolefins (2-4) provided 3 β -methoxy-6 β -nitrocholest-4-ene (6; 0.80 g, 80%), m.p. 116° (Found: C, 75.6; H, 10.6; N, 3.1. $C_{28}H_{47}NO_3$ requires: C, 75.5; H, 10.57; N, 3.14%); (negative Beilstein test); ν_{max} 1545, 1470 and 1375 (non-conjugated NO_2) and 1080 cm^{-1} (OCH_3); δ 5.96 (br, s, C4-vinyl proton), 4.63 (dd, J_{ae} 5, J_{ee} 2.5 Hz, C6- α H), 5.13 (m, $W_{1/2}$ 18 Hz, C3- α H), 3.32 (s, OCH_3), 1.2 (C10- CH_3), 0.7 (C13- CH_3), 0.93 and 0.83 (other methyl protons) and 3 β -hydroxy-6 β -nitrocholest-4-ene (7; 0.86 g, 86%), m.p. and m.m.p. 154° (lit.⁹ 154.5-155°) (Found: C, 75.2; H, 10.4; N, 3.4. $C_{27}H_{46}NO_3$ requires: C, 75.1; H, 10.3; N, 3.2%); ν_{max} 3450 (OH), 1540, 1350 and 1375 cm^{-1} (non-conjugated NO_2); δ 5.85 (br, s, C4-vinyl proton), 4.63 (dd, J_{ae} 4, J_{ee} 2 Hz, C6- α H), 4.12 (m, $W_{1/2}$ 18 Hz, C3- α H), 1.2 (C10- CH_3), 0.73 (C13- CH_3), 0.93 and 0.83 (other methyl protons).

Acetylation of 7: 3 β -Hydroxy-6 β -nitrocholest-4-ene (7; 100 mg) was treated with purified pyridine (1 ml) and freshly distilled acetic anhydride (0.8 ml) and warmed on a water-bath for 2 h. The reaction mixture was poured into water and solid thus obtained was air-dried. Recrystallisation of solid from acetone gave 3 β -acetoxy-6 β -nitrocholest-4-ene (8; 0.72 g, 72%), m.p. and m.m.p. 101° (lit.⁹ 101-102°) (Found: C, 73.7; H, 10.1; N, 3.0. $C_{29}H_{47}NO_3$ requires: C, 73.6; H, 9.9; N, 2.9%); ν_{max} 1730 (CH_3COO), 1545, 1465 and 1375 cm^{-1} (non-conjugated NO_2); δ 5.75 (br, s, C4-vinyl proton), 4.58 (dd, J_{ae} 4, J_{ee} 2 Hz, C6- α H), 2.0 (s, C3- β -O- $COCH_3$), 1.18 (C10- CH_3), 0.70 (C13- CH_3), 0.90 and 0.79 (other methyl protons).

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Synthesis of some New Carboxanilides and Amides of 8-Methoxycoumarin-3-carboxylic Acid as Possible Antifungal and Antibacterial Agents

SONAL SHAH and R. H. MBHTA*

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science,
M. S. University of Baroda, Baroda-390 002

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COUMARIN derivatives are known to have antifungal and antibacterial properties¹⁻³. On the other hand, haloacetamides^{4,5} possess amoebicidal activity and substituted-acetamides^{6,7} have local anaesthetic property. With a view to prepare better therapeutically active compound the present work is undertaken.

The present paper deals with the synthesis of some anilides and amides by reaction of 8-methoxycoumarin-3-carboxylic acid⁸ (1) via acid chloride with aliphatic, alicyclic, aromatic and heterocyclic primary and secondary amines. The structures of the compounds were assigned on the basis of their satisfactory elemental analysis, ir and pmr spectra.

Experimental

M.ps. are uncorrected. Microanalysis of compounds were performed on a Coleman instrument, ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu 408 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer using TMS as the internal standard.

8-Methoxycoumarin-3-carboxanilides and amides: The acid chloride was prepared by refluxing 8-methoxycoumarin-3-carboxylic acid (2 g) with thionyl chloride (4 ml) and dry benzene (50 ml) until the solution was clear (3 h). The excess thionyl chloride and benzene were distilled off. To the acid chloride in dry ether (60 ml), two mole equivalent of the amine was added. The mixture was then stirred for 3 h, cooled and filtered. The solid product was dried and washed with water. The product was crystallised from the proper solvent. The physical data of compounds 2 and 3 are presented in Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 2

Sl. no.*	R	R ₁	M p.°C**	Yield %
1.	C ₆ H ₅ -	H	232 ^b	80
2 ^a	<i>o</i> -Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	255 ^c	85
3 ^a	<i>p</i> -Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	197 ^c	82
4 ^a	<i>p</i> -Br-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	259 ^b	75
5.	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	H	94 ^d	95
6	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	H	91 ^d	76
7	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	H	235 ^b	82
8	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	H	246 ^b	85
9	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	H	230 ^b	73
10 ^a	<i>p</i> -COOC ₂ H ₅ -C ₆ H ₄ -	H	241 ^b	86
11.	<i>o</i> -NH ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	H	228 ^b	81
12.	<i>p</i> -Br-C ₆ H ₄ -	Br	265 ^e	65
13.	α -Naphthyl	H	239 ^b	79
14.	β -Naphthyl	H	246 ^b	80
15	Cyclohexyl	H	160 ^b	74
16	4-Phenylthiazol-2	H	294 ^b	62

* Compounds tested for antifungal and antibacterial activities. ** Crystallisation solvent: ^bchloroform, ^cbenzene, ^dDMSO, ^ebenzene+ethanol

TABLE 2 PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3

Sl. no.	R ₁	R ₂	M p.°C	Yield %
1.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	215 ^b	73
2.	C ₇ H ₇	C ₆ H ₅	193 ^b	75
3.	C ₈ H ₉	C ₆ H ₅	120 ^f	73
R ₂ = R ₁				
4. ^a	Morpholine		189 ^b	69
5.	N-Phenylpiperazine		162 ^g	91

* Compounds tested for antifungal and antibacterial activities. ** Crystallisation solvent: ^bchloroform, ^cwater, ^dbenzene+ethanol

The ir spectra shows characteristic absorption bands at 3 400 br (NH), 1 720 (C=O of coumarin) and 1 600 cm⁻¹ (aromatic C=C ring stretch). It also exhibited an amide I band at 1 670–1 650 cm⁻¹ and amide II band at 1 560–1 540 cm⁻¹. Compound 3 (Table 2) did not exhibit the above bands, instead C=O absorption^g (of 3^o amide) was observed at 1 680–1 630 cm⁻¹. Pmr (90 MHz) spectra revealed the following: 8-methoxycoumarin-3-carboxyanilide (Table 1; 2, Sl. no. 1) δ (CDCl₃) 3.98 (3H, s, OCH₃), 7.1–7.7 (m br, Ar) and 8.86 (1H, s, H-4); 8-methoxycoumarin-3-carboxy-(N-phenyl)anilide (Table 2; 3, Sl. no. 1) δ (CF₃COOH) 3.6 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.9–7.1 (m br, Ar), 8.0 (1H, s, 4-H).

Antifungal and antibacterial activity: Some selected compounds were tested for their antifungal and antibacterial activity in DMF and benzene solvents *in vitro* 8-Methoxycoumarin-3-carboxy-(*p*-bromo)anilide was found to be active against the fungi *Cryptococcus neoformans* (activity, 25 μ g ml⁻¹) and *Sporotrichum schenckii* (activity, 25 μ g ml⁻¹). 8-Methoxy-6-bromocoumarin-3-carboxy-*p*-bromo-anilide was active against the fungi *Trichophyton mentagrophytes* (activity, 25 μ g ml⁻¹) and rest of the compounds were found to be inactive against the fungi. None of the compounds tested (MIC in

100 μ g ml⁻¹) was found to have antibacterial activity.

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Synthesis of 2-(3-Coumarinyl)-4(1H)-anthryridinones

K. RAJENDAR REDDY, K. MOGILAI AH
and

B SREFNIVASULU*

Department of Chemistry, Kakatiya University,
Warangal-506 009

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A survey of the literature revealed that very little work has been reported on the synthesis of anthryridines¹⁻³. In continuation of our work on the synthesis of anthryridines⁴, we report herein the synthesis of 2-(3-coumarinyl)-2(1H)anthryridinones (Scheme 1).

2-Amino-3-cyano-1,8-naphthyridine (1) was obtained by the condensation of 2-aminonicotinaldehyde with malonitrile in ethanol with piperidine as catalyst⁵. Condensation of 1 with 3-acetylcoumarins (2) in glacial acetic acid with a catalytic amount of concentrated sulphuric acid resulted in the formation of 2-(3-coumarinyl)-4(1H)anthryridinones (3) in good yield. The structures of these compounds were in conformity with their elemental analyses and spectral (ir and mass) data. A comparison of the ir spectra of 3 with those of immediate